

Evaluating airflow dynamics in operating rooms: a comparative study of low-cost and high-end air velocity sensors

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Abstract. For indoor environmental control, especially in healthcare settings, precise understanding of airflow distribution is crucial due to its impact on energy efficiency, environmental comfort, and most critically, occupant health. Accurate airflow measurement is vital in operating rooms (ORs), where the quality of air directly influences surgical outcomes and patient safety. This study focuses on evaluating the performance of low-cost airflow monitoring systems in capturing the real pattern of laminar airflow in an OR lab, a key factor in maintaining a sterile surgical environment. To this end, the study employs an array of sensors, including low-cost Omron MEMS Flow sensors, intermediate AirDisSys 5000 anemometers, and the high-end Testo 400 air velocity probe, were placed at four levels from the operating table to the laminar airflow diffuser. Following calibration of low-cost sensors using Testo 400, those sensors conducted measurements at various levels in comparison to the data from Testo 400 and AirDisSys 5000. The advanced Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) technique was employed for detailed analysis of the crucial area next to an imaginary patients wound, indicating strong turbulence there. Results reveals that the airflow turbulence intensity near the wound surface significantly increases, rising from below 5% to around 15%, meanwhile, the relative error of low-cost sensors also grows as the airflow nears the wound surface. The results of this comparative analysis provide a nuanced understanding of the performance of various air velocity measurement instruments, highlighting their respective strengths and limitations. This information is invaluable for both academic research and real-world applications, guiding healthcare facilities in enhancing their air monitoring systems.

1 Introduction

Airflow distribution inside buildings is an important topic in environmental engineering and health research, especially in delicate situations like operating rooms (ORs). Energy efficiency, environmental comfort, and, most significantly, occupant health are all affected by how well we understand airflow patterns, so it's clear that this isn't just a theoretical issue [1]. Establishing a clean environment during surgical operations, and controlling airflow is critical in ORs to decrease the risk of Surgical Site Infection (SSI) [2]. Aiming to close the gap between affordable and accurate airflow measuring methods, this study compares the performance of low-cost sensors with more traditional, high-cost approaches.

It has been common for an extended period of time to evaluate airflow in indoor environments by striking a balance between cost and accuracy. Although cutting-edge Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) systems and analogous equipment provide very precise outcomes, they may be prohibitively expensive and complex to operate [3]. Conversely, inexpensive sensors provide a cost-effective alternative; nevertheless, their dependability and precision in complex airflow settings such as ORs remain unknown. One critical factor in

maintaining sterile environments inside healthcare facilities, particularly ORs, is the airflow distribution, which influences the way in which airborne contaminants are dispersed [4][5]. According to Mancini et al. [6], an excessive volume of airflow may lead to elevated energy consumption, resulting in increased operational expenses.

PIV has attracted attention for its precise spatial resolution and excellent accuracy when it comes to measuring methods used to capture airflow patterns [7][8]. Abdulwahab et al. [9] have observed that PIV systems use sophisticated optical methods to see and quantify the velocity field inside fluid flows; hence, although they are exceptionally efficient, they are also prohibitively costly and technically challenging. The complexity of these systems restricts their applicability to regular monitoring in several indoor environment. On the contrary, anemometers have achieved extensive use owing to their optimal combination of affordability, user-friendliness, and satisfactory precision. Anemometers are available in a range of configurations, as described by Korprasertsak and Leephakpreeda [10]. These configurations include vane, hot-wire, and ultrasonic kinds, and each has distinct merits and drawbacks with regard to reaction time, sensitivity, and spatial resolution. These devices have been used

extensively in practical applications and investigations because to their favorable cost-to-precision ratio [11]. However, the emergence of inexpensive sensors has introduced novel prospects in the realm of airflow monitoring. Recent advancements in Micro-Electro-Mechanical System (MEMS) technology have enabled the production of inexpensive, small sensors capable of measuring air velocity and other environmental factors [12][13]. For instance, OMRON MEMS Flow sensors demonstrate this emerging technological trend. On account of their economical nature and seamless compatibility with platforms such as Raspberry Pi, they may serve as a practical solution for facilitating continuous and wide environmental monitoring. Despite their merits, the precision and dependability of inexpensive sensors in complex airflow conditions such as ORs remain to be investigated.

This gap in the literature's knowledge raises the need for comprehensive research that evaluates these low-cost sensors in actual settings. This study does a comparative analysis of the performance of OMRON MEMS Flow sensors, anemometers and PIV systems in order to get a more comprehensive knowledge of their efficacy in environments such as ORs. The outcomes of this study have significance for practical implementations as well as for the overall understanding and control of indoor airflow dynamics.

2 Methodology

This study aims to evaluate the precision of low-cost airflow sensors compared to more conventional, high-priced measuring techniques. The primary focus of this assessment is the accurate measurement of laminar airflow in an OR lab, where maintaining sterile conditions requires careful management of airflow. Using this method, anemometers, PIV systems, and economical sensors will be compared in depth.

2.1 Experimental setup

The experiment was carried out inside a controlled OR lab environment. Laminar airflow (LAF) systems, which are often used in surgical environments to reduce the likelihood of airborne contamination, were installed in the room. The OR lab dimension is 7.0 m x 8.7 m x 3.1 m (W x L x H). The experimental configuration included the positioning of diverse airflow measuring instruments at four different heights, ranging from the level of the operating table to that of the laminar airflow diffuser.

The OR lab features two ventilation systems: laminar airflow and mixing ventilation. Its laminar airflow ceiling, with a 3m x 3m air supply area, is positioned in the room's center, surrounded by mixing ventilation terminals. However, these mixing diffusers were blocked for the duration of this study. Uniform HVAC settings were maintained in the room throughout the experiment in order to preserve a controlled environment. The temperature and flow rate of the supply air are 22.6 °C and 14500 m³/h, respectively. The positive pressure level inside an OR lab was set at

15 Pa. This experimental configuration employs three distinct categories of measuring devices, spanning from inexpensive sensors to very costly instrumentation.

2.1.1 Low-cost sensors

The Omron D6F-W01A1 sensor was chosen for this investigation owing to its cost-effectiveness and straightforward integration into our experimental configuration. The device employs a thermal mass flow method for measuring airflow velocity, utilizing a silicon substrate with a heater and thermopiles on both sides. This setup detects changes in heat transfer caused by airflow over its thin film, allowing for the detection of minute airflow rate variations [14]. With a measuring range of less than 1m/s, the sensor is well suited for identifying minute airflow patterns in the vicinity of LAF in an OR lab environment.

A Raspberry Pi microcontroller was used in combination with two Omron D6F-W01A1 sensors to capture and analyze the data. Its decision was eventually determined by the flexibility, affordability, and adaptability of Raspberry Pi in processing data from a vast array of sensors. This method was effective for collecting data in real-time and doing preliminary analysis on-site. The ADS1115 analogue-to-digital converter module was used to convert the output voltage generated by the Omron sensors into digital values. The module's connection with the Raspberry Pi is conducted via the I2C standard, which ensures accurate and efficient data transmission.

It was not possible to provide the Omron sensors with direct power from the Raspberry Pi, in contrast to some other inexpensive sensors, due to their power needs ranging from 12 to 24 V. As a result, we choose to implement an alternate power source by connecting two 9V batteries in series. The aforementioned methodology yielded a reliable and constant power supply; however, it required careful inspection to guarantee continuous functioning for the course of the experiment.

2.1.2 Anemometers

For detailed airflow measurement in this research, two distinct anemometers were utilized: the AirDisSys 5000 and the Testo 400 air velocity probe. Both devices are well recognized for their accuracy and dependability for evaluating airflow, which makes them well-suited for our experimental configuration. Designed to provide accurate readings of low air velocity and air temperature in a variety of room environments, the AirDisSys 5000 is an advanced air distribution sampling device. In this experiment, four velocity probes were linked to the AirDisSys 5000. These probes were strategically placed from 5 cm above the patient table level (L1) to 5 cm below the ceiling (L4), with two additional probes positioned at intermediate levels, as depicted in Figure 1. The spacing between each level was maintained at 67 cm. In order to record the dynamic airflow patterns across several horizontal planes in the OR lab, this

configuration was used to gather a wide variety of data points.

A Testo 400 equipped with a turbulence probe is also included into the configuration. With exceptional accuracy, this lightweight probe measures air velocity and temperature, even at low air velocities. The minimal size of the device enabled a more adaptable arrangement in the OR lab, ensuring that regular operations were not disrupted.

2.1.3 Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV)

As a baseline for high-cost and precise evaluation, PIV measurements were performed. PIV measurements were limited to a single height level, with a primary emphasis on the region in close proximity to the surgical wound site on the operating table, as a result of resource limitations.

Flow visualization is used in connection with these observations at planar PIV. Comparing the measured velocity and turbulence intensity with those of low-cost sensors and anemometers. The PIV measurements are performed using the CCD camera LX 6M in conjunction with a specific laser (Nd: YAG laser Litron Nano L 200-15 150 mJ), operating in double frame mode at a sampling rate of 12.8 Hz and a wavelength of 532 nm. An aerosol generator is used to inject DEHS oil as a seeding material, with an average droplet diameter of 1 μm . Over the manikin wound, the interrogation area has a width of 104 mm and a height of 85 mm when the cross-correlation window is 32×32 pixels and the reference time between frames is $dt = 2800 \mu\text{s}$, respectively. In this study, we used a thermal manikin with a 55W heating gain, and the room was unoccupied during measurements.

The technical specifications of measurement techniques in this experiment are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Technical specifications of various measurement techniques

Measurement device	Measuring range	Accuracy
Omron D6F-W01A1	0 to 1 m/s	$\pm 5\%mv$ (0.05 m/s)
AirDisSys 5000	0.05 to 5 m/s	$\pm 0.02\text{m/s} \pm 1\%$ of v
Testo 400 – turbulence probe	0 to 5 m/s	$\pm(0.03 \text{ m/s} + 4 \% \text{ of mv})$

2.2 Sensor placement and data collection

In order to assure the gathering of comparable data, Omron low-cost sensors, AirDisSys 5000 probes, and Testo 400 probes were strategically positioned next to one another on each level of the operating room. Particularly, at each measurement level, two inexpensive sensors were implemented in order to provide a comprehensive evaluation of their recording capabilities. The full arrangement of various sensors in the OR lab is visually shown in Figure 1.

Placing the sensors in a manner that prevented the risk of cross - contamination with one another's airflow

readings. The data collecting process spanned a duration of 15 minutes for each level. The recording time intervals also set to possible minimum value which is 0.25 seconds, 1 second, and 2 seconds for the Omron, Testo 400, and AirDisSys 5000 sensors, respectively.

In order to capture the dynamic character of airflow patterns, this time interval was selected to provide a comprehensive examination of transient behaviors and time-dependent variations. The allocation of 15 minutes allows for the observation and documentation of consistent airflow patterns across a range of operational circumstances.

Figure 1. Detailed placement of sensors within the OR lab; Top view: Raspberry Pi arrangement, Middle view: all sensors and PIV camera placement, Bottom view: different levels of sensors placement

2.3 Data processing and analysis

When the data recording was completed, an intensive data processing and analysis approach were carried out, which included the following:

Data cleaning: During this first stage, the data were processed in order to eliminate any abnormalities and outliers that may have introduced bias into the findings. For the purpose of ensuring consistency across all levels, the time duration for each measurement set was standardized to precisely fifteen minutes. Additionally, in order to assist a more obvious study of patterns and trends, the data were averaged across 10 seconds.

Comparative analysis: During this stage, the measurements received from the low-cost sensors were thoroughly compared to the readings obtained from the anemometers and the PIV system. For the purpose of this comparison, the main objective was to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the low-cost sensors in terms of their capacity to capture airflow patterns. To do this, it was necessary to determine the degree to which the readings obtained from the low-cost sensors were comparable to those obtained from the more established and high-end measuring equipment.

Statistical analysis: To enhance the robustness of the assessment, statistical techniques were used. Furthermore, a linear regression approach was used to discover the linear correlation between the low-cost sensors and the reference sensor, in addition to error analysis (for calibration purpose). The linearity of the connection was evaluated by the process of fitting a linear model to the data obtained from the low-cost sensors in comparison to the reference sensors. The significance levels (R-squared, intercept, and slope) derived from the regression analysis provide insightful information on the performance of the inexpensive sensors in comparison to the benchmark systems.

3 Results

3.1 Low-cost sensor calibration

Calibration of the inexpensive Omron sensors was an essential component of this investigation in order to guarantee the precision and dependability of the findings. The data from the recently purchased Testo 400 sensor, which was accompanied by a verified calibration is used, as the benchmark for calibrating the inexpensive sensors. By using this methodology, we were able to synchronize the functionality of the Omron sensors with a well-acknowledged and reliable standard, thereby boosting the credibility of the empirical findings.

In order to carry out this calibration procedure, the Testo velocity probe and the low-cost sensors were positioned strategically in close proximity to the extract opening of the OR lab. The rationale for choosing this location was its comparatively consistent airflow, a critical factor in ensuring precise and accurate calibration. Airflow was measured at three distinct velocity settings, spanning from low to high, as part of the calibration procedure. A total of 15 minutes was

allocated to each configuration in order to gather thorough data under a variety of scenarios. The recorded results of this process are presented in Figure 2.

Furthermore, in the calibration procedure, a linear correlation was established between the low-cost Omron sensors and the Testo reference sensor by using a linear regression strategy. In order to do this, the dataset including the mean values of each velocity setting from the Omron sensors in comparison to the Testo sensor was subjected to a linear regression model. Figure 3 shows the outcomes of this investigation. The metrics derived from the regression study were of critical importance to modify the recording with low-cost sensors. The metrics included the values of slope, intercept, and R-squared. The linear model effectively provided a strong correlation between two Omron and Testo 400 sensors' readings, as shown by the very high R-squared values of 0.999 and 0.996. The modified velocity determined by the regression equation is used by inexpensive sensors in the following sections.

Figure 2. Recording data of Testo 4000 and Omron low-cost sensors (V_rpi1, V_rpi2)

Figure 3. Linear regression plot

3.2 Distribution of airflow dynamics

An essential component of this research, the evaluation of airflow distribution in the OR lab revealed the LAF system's efficacy in preserving a regulated environment. The research was mostly grounded on the

velocity data obtained from the Testo 400 sensor, which provided a trustworthy indicator for airflow patterns.

Through careful examination of the recorded velocity data from the Testo 400, we were able to delineate the airflow distribution supplying from the LAF diffuser, especially at level L4, which is near the ceiling, down to the critical area around the surgical wound at level L1 on the operating table. The results of this analysis, as depicted in Figure 4, offer a detailed visualization of how air travels and disperses across these levels. Furthermore, the mean value and standard deviation are computed for every collection of time-series data and illustrated in error bar chart. These computations provide further insights into the airflow profile, shedding light on its mean characteristics as well as the degree of variation at each level.

Figure 4. Airflow distribution across various height levels as recorded by the Testo 400 velocity probe

3.3 Comparative analysis of sensors readings

This section provides a comparative analysis of sensor data obtained from different heights inside the OR lab. This comparison underscores the performance of the inexpensive sensors in contrast to their more advanced and accurate counterparts.

Due to the complex and time-consuming characteristics of PIV measurements, this technique was solely used at the most critical region in close proximity to the surgical wound. Due to its high sensitivity, PIV is well-suited for this measurement, ensuring an extremely accurate representation of airflow in the exact location where it significantly impacts health outcomes.

To measure how well the inexpensive sensors worked, their readings to those of the AirDisSys 5000 and Testo 400 were compared to calculate the percentage error. The resulting percentage errors are tabulated in Table 2, which offers a concise reference for the accuracy of each sensor type at different levels. These calculated relative errors for low-cost sensors occurred despite applying calibration correction.

The findings of airflow velocity measurement using PIV at the wound level, where the greatest variations were seen, are shown in Figure 6. Due to the need to have a detailed and accurate measurement, planar PIV is employed to carefully observe the airflow's dynamic behavior. Using this method, we were able to collect nearly 12 data points per second from the PIV system throughout our exhaustive 6-minute assessment.

Figure 7 depicts three sequential snapshots of airflow velocity at the wound level using PIV, captured within a one-minute interval. Diverse colors and overlaid

vectors show the velocities and directions of airflow across the surgical wound. The picture clearly shows that the airflow is quite variable, with the unidirectional pattern disturbed, particularly around the area of the wound.

Figure 5. Velocity measurements in various height levels with AirDisSys 5000 (V_{ads}), Testo 400 (V_{testo}) and low-cost sensors (V_{rpi1} , V_{rpi2})

Figure 6. Time history of absolute air velocity, captured 5 cm above the patient wound (L1), using PIV technique

Table 2. Reading error of low-cost sensors

Height level	Error (%) relative to Testo 400		Error (%) relative to AirDisSys 5000	
	rpi1	rpi2	rpi1	rpi2
L1	20.22	29.69	9.51	20.25
L2	10.50	16.84	10.79	17.11
L3	11.40	16.50	11.87	16.94
L4	7.72	14.50	6.32	13.21

3.4 Turbulence intensity evaluation

The evaluation of turbulence intensity in the OR lab is important to our work because it gives vital information on airflow dynamics and the impacts of such dynamics on the sterility of the surgical zone. By

using the data obtained from each sensor, we proceed to calculate the turbulence intensity at different height levels using Equation 1. Turbulence intensity (Tu) is a dimensionless parameter that represents the degree of fluctuation in airflow velocity. It is defined as [15]:

$$Tu = \frac{\sigma_v}{\bar{v}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where σ_v represents the standard deviation of the velocity, indicative of the variability in the airflow speed, and \bar{v} is the mean velocity, reflecting the average speed of airflow across a given time interval.

Figure 7. Distribution of air velocity at wound level captured in three sequential snapshots within a one-minute interval

The velocity data is averaged across 30-second intervals for turbulence intensity calculation. Within the same time frame, we also determine the standard deviation, which is a measure of the dispersion of the airflow around its mean value. Figure 8 shows the results of the turbulence intensity assessment in two different visual formats: a boxplot and a linear graph. Because airflow patterns are dynamic, the linear graph shows how the turbulence intensity varies over time. The boxplot, on the other hand, is a statistical summary that shows the data's extremes—its maximum and lowest values—as well as the median and interquartile range (which encompasses the 25th to the 75th percentile).

Figure 8. Comparison of turbulence intensity at various height levels measured by different sensors

4 Discussion

4.1 Air distribution in LAF system

To determine how well the LAF system works inside the OR lab, it is necessary to analyze the data on airflow distribution obtained by the Testo 400 velocity probe (see Figure 4). The distribution of airflow from the ceiling (L4) to the operating table (L1) predicts a considerable gradient in velocity for descending airflow. The observed fluctuations suggest that the airflow is not entirely laminar throughout the height, particularly at the two lowest levels where visible air turbulence occurs. The presence of a thermal manikin has an effect on the velocity gradient observed from the LAF diffuser to the wound area. The airflow parameters are likely to be altered by the thermal plume created by thermal manikin at desk level, where there is a considerable reduction in velocity and an increase in fluctuations. A perfect laminar flow may be disturbed by these thermal effects, leading to an upward thermal flow that might counteract the downward sterile airflow.

The mean velocities show that the LAF system generally maintains a downward airflow, which is necessary for cleaning the air. However, as seen by the standard deviations at each level, concern about the airflow variation should be examined further. The heat generated by the manikin is most likely responsible for the considerable change in airflow at the wound level; this implies turbulence, which might harm the sterile field by trapping contaminants. Furthermore, comparing the uniform airflow at level L4 and the variation at level L1 could result in the interpretation of the LAF system's efficiency reduction when the airflow approaches sensitive surgical zones. If LAF systems are to be designed and operated in a way that guarantees a steady and uniform airflow where it is most required, then it is crucial to understand these dynamics.

4.2 Airflow fluctuation in OR lab

By comparing sensor data at various heights within an OR lab, significant insights into the trade-offs between sensor cost and accuracy are revealed. While low-cost sensors (V_rpi1, V_rpi2) provide such an affordable alternative to more expensive versions for airflow monitoring, the results show that they indicate more turbulence, especially when the height is changed, compared to the more advanced AirDisSys 5000 and Testo 400 types. This may be attributed to the shorter time constant of the Omron sensors used in this experiment, which allows for quicker responses but can also result in varied fluctuations. As seen in the table of percentage errors, there is a noticeable difference. This suggests that essential measurements near surgical incisions or other areas with high levels of airflow fluctuation may not be accurately measured with inexpensive sensors. Despite its complexity and time-intensiveness, PIV is essential in critical zones due to its high accuracy, which is in line with the requirement for accurate characterization of airflow to minimize infection risks.

The visual representation in Figure 7 provides a clear indication that the airflow is not uniform close to wound area. Low-cost sensors have restricted measuring capabilities, detecting only airflow vectors that meet their apertures and so omitting velocity components, notably horizontal vectors and vertical vectors with reverse orientation. Omnidirectional anemometers, on the other hand, measure the magnitude of velocity across all vectors but do not differentiate their direction. With its full capture of both the magnitude and direction of each vector, PIV gives a holistic perspective of the airflow, enabling the total velocity to be calculated. This methodology causes PIV to provide lower velocity estimates (shown in Figure 6) than anemometers, which may overestimate velocity by aggregating all vector magnitudes regardless of direction. The gap in results between various sensor types emphasizes the need to carefully consider sensor capabilities and limits when monitoring airflow, particularly in the sensitive environment.

The implications of these findings are multifaceted. While inexpensive sensors may not be the best choice for highly precise airflow monitoring in less crucial

zones, such as levels L3 and L4, where the airflow is more constant and unidirectional, they could still provide useful information for regulating the overall air quality in the OR lab. With this tiered approach to sensor placement, it is feasible to optimize resource allocation without losing measurement precision or patient safety at the wound level. Therefore, it means that improving resource efficiency, maintaining measurement integrity, and ensuring patient safety at the wound site may be achieved by adopting a tiered approach for sensor deployment.

Subtle but significant discrepancies in readings were found when comparing the two newly installed, inexpensive sensors. Considering their near proximity during installation, these discrepancies in reading might potentially be attributed to a multitude of factors, including variations in individual calibration or influences from the environment. While there is scope for improvement, the data consistency between low-cost sensors suggests that inexpensive sensors might potentially serve as a feasible alternative for monitoring non-critical environments, provided that their constraints are acknowledged and accounted for.

4.3 Turbulence intensity

Figure 8 shows the results of turbulence intensity measurements taken by various sensors at different heights. It can be seen that there is a rise in LAF fluctuations as the airflow gets closer to the wound surface. The results show that while the average turbulence intensities recorded by all sensors were less than 5% before approaching the wound surface, they increased by about 15% as they got closer to the patient. This pattern highlights an important finding: when the airflow approaches the wound surface, there is a noticeable increase in turbulence, which may affect the sterile field.

Moreover, the findings shed light on the performance of low-cost sensors in comparison to more advanced anemometers. Despite some minor deviations, the low-cost sensors demonstrate a capacity to predict turbulence intensity with a good accuracy specially compared with Testo 400. Implications for the monitoring and maintenance of sterile conditions in surgical situations might be substantial if these inexpensive sensors can approximate the turbulence intensity values of their more sophisticated equivalents.

5 Conclusion

This research investigates the performance of inexpensive sensors in quantifying airflow and analyzes the air distribution and turbulence characteristics of an OR lab that incorporates a LAF system. Three distinct air velocity measuring techniques are used in the experiment: inexpensive sensors (Omron MEMS sensor), intermediately priced devices (Testo 400 and AirDisSys 5000 anemometers), and an expensive approach (PIV).

The following are key observations:

- Low-cost Omron D6F-W01A1 sensors have shown satisfactory performance for monitoring airflow in non-critical areas of the OR lab where the airflow is laminar and unidirectional. They recorded a relative air velocity error ranging from 6.3% to 17.1%. Furthermore, the turbulence intensity calculated using both these low-cost sensors and high-end anemometer readings was below 5%, indicating their acceptable accuracy for specific applications.
- High-precision instruments, such as the Testo 400 and PIV, are essential for accurate airflow measurement in areas of high variability, crucial to maintaining an aseptic surgical environment.
- Variation in sensor readings, even among identical low-cost devices, indicates the need for careful calibration and consideration of environmental factors in sensor deployment.
- In the OR lab, the LAF system effectively maintains downward sterile airflow, but heat sources near the wound site can induce turbulence, risking sterile field integrity.
- In the OR lab, there is a significant increase in airflow turbulence as it approaches the wound surface, with turbulence intensities rising from below 5% to approximately 15% near the patient.
- The study advocates for a tiered approach to sensor placement, aligning sensor accuracy and cost with the varying criticality of different zones within the OR lab.

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